

SUPPORTING INFORMATION FOR “DIURNAL TO SEASONAL DYNAMICS OF
SALINE PAN EVAPORATION AND GROUNDWATER FLUCTUATIONS,
BONNEVILLE SALT FLATS UTAH, USA”

Introduction

This supplemental file contains supporting information describing data sources, data processing steps, and supplemental figures. The data quality control, gap-filling, and Matlab (MathWorks, 2020) analyses code used for this study is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5671739> and the datasets that support this work are archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5634172> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4268710>. These datasets consist of modern and historical meteorological and groundwater measurements.

Text S1. Meteorological data

Meteorological measurements and products are archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5634172>. The data quality control, gap-filling, and Matlab (MathWorks, 2020) analyses code used for this study are archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5671739>.

S1.1. Meteorological measurements and surface observations

Historical meteorological measurements from the Bonneville Salt Flats and the surrounding area were reported by Lines (1979) and Mason and Kipp (1998). Additional measurements from Wendover, Utah, were collected from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Climate Data Online Portal. These measurements were used to examine the spatial and temporal heterogeneity of precipitation and evaporation in the area surrounding BSF (Figure S1).

S1.2. Meteorological data gap filling

The weather station was installed with limited radiation measurement capabilities on September 29, 2016. Longwave radiation measurements were not available prior to the installation of the longwave radiometers on June 6, 2017, radiation measurements prior to this period are described by Craft and Horel (2018). Outgoing and net longwave radiometer measurements from November 24, 2019 to March 2, 2020 were removed from the dataset for quality control. An artificial neural network was shown to estimate radiation effectively by Kelley (2020). The neural network (using the methods outlined in Text S3, and with the training inputs of air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed,

incoming and outgoing shortwave radiation, and time of day) was used to fill data gaps. The artificial neural network was more effective at estimating net longwave radiation than incoming longwave radiation (Figure S3). Incoming longwave radiation was calculated by subtracting the outgoing radiation from net longwave radiation for data gaps filled with neural network data.

From June 9 to 11, 2019, the weather station did not log meteorological measurements. Temperature, humidity, air pressure, and incoming shortwave radiation measurement from this period were replaced with measurements made by the nearby DPG17 weather station (<https://mesowest.utah.edu/>, station ID: DPG17). Outgoing shortwave radiation and incoming and outgoing longwave radiation during this period were replaced with measured mean BSF radiation measurements from the preceding and proceeding days.

A data gap from January 1 to 26, 2022 was filled by using air pressure, relative humidity, and solar radiation from the LMR (<https://mesowest.utah.edu/>, station ID: LMR) station. Closer weather stations did not measure appropriate variables or also had data gaps during this period. Additional variables were filled with historical average measurements based upon the September 2016 to April 2022 dataset.

S1.3. Eddy-covariance data and aerodynamic roughness

The eddy-covariance equipment was oriented to the northwest and installed at the height of 2.57 m from May to August 2018. Eddy-covariance data available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5634172> and the code used to determine the aerodynamic roughness length is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5671739>.

The aerodynamic roughness length (Z_o) (meters) was determined with sonic anemometer data collected from May to August 2018 with equation S1-1. Equation S1-1 is rearranged to solve for Z_o in equation S1-2; the data is filtered where L is > 100 m, such that $\Psi_m\left(\frac{Z}{L}\right)$ approaches zero (Stull, 2012).

$$\frac{\bar{m}}{u_*} = 1/K \left(\ln \left(\frac{Z}{Z_o} \right) + \Psi_m \left(\frac{Z}{L} \right) \right) \quad (S1-1)$$

$$Z_o = Z / \exp \left(K \frac{\bar{m}}{u_*} \right) \quad (S1-2)$$

where

Z_o is the aerodynamic roughness length (m);

\bar{m} is wind speed (m/s) filtered to only include wind speeds between 2-6 m/s;

μ^* is the friction velocity (m/s), K is the von Karman Constant (0.4);

Z is the measurement height (m);

Ψ_m is the stability function; and

L is the Monin-Obukhov length scale.

The median value of Z_o at BSF was $5.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m.

S1.4. Wind-related precipitation undercatch

Precipitation can be notoriously undermeasured because of wind-related turbulence contributing to rain gauge undercatch. To address potential wind-related undercatch the corrections of Yang and others (1996) were applied:

$$R_{solid} = \exp (4.606 - 0.157U^{1.28}) \quad (S1-3)$$

$$R_{mixed} = 100.77 - 8.34U \quad (S1-4)$$

$$R_{liquid} = \exp(4.605 - 0.062U^{0.58}) \quad (S1-5)$$

$$PPT_t = \frac{P_m}{R} * 100 \quad (S1-6)$$

where

R is precipitation delineated by phase (solid: temperature < -2 °C; mixed: temperature -2 to 3 °C; and liquid: temperature > 3 °C);

U is mean daily wind speed at precipitation gauge height (m/s);

P_t is total daily precipitation (mm); and

P_m is measured daily precipitation (mm).

Daily average temperatures were used to delineate what condition applied to *R*. Because measurements at the height of the rain gauge (1 m) were unavailable, the log wind profile (equation XX) was used to correct anemometer wind measurements (3 m above surface level) to wind at the height of the rain gauge (Holmes, 2015).

$$U_{gauge} = U_{anem} * \frac{\ln(Z_{gauge}/Z_0)}{\ln(Z_{anem}/Z_0)} \quad (S1-7)$$

where

U_{gauge} is the windspeed at the rain gauge elevation (m/s);

U_{anem} is the anemometer windspeed (m/s);

Z_{gauge} is rain gauge height (m);

Z_{anem} is anemometer height (m); and

Z₀ is the aerodynamic roughness length (m).

Sonic anemometer data were used to calculate BSF's aerodynamic roughness (de Bruin & Holstag, 1982; Nield et al., 2013) (Text S1.3). Applying this correction for

elevation led to a 29% average decrease in wind speed relative to the anemometer (from 4.7 to 3.4 m/s). The actual windspeed at the bucket gauge may be less than determined by this method because of the chain-link enclosure surrounding the weather station and the rain gauge. This additional decrease in windspeed at the rain gauge would reduce precipitation undercatch relative to our calculated value.

S1.5. Imagery

The saline pan's surface properties and surface features changed over time with evaporite growth, dissolution, and alteration. Time-lapse imagery from the BFLAT weather station is available at http://home.chpc.utah.edu/~u0790486/wxinfo/cgi-bin/uunet_camera_explorer.cgi Camera: Bonneville Salt Flats, and, along with imagery from other locations at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4171331> (Bernau & Bowen, 2021). There are some gaps within the weather station-collected imagery because of equipment malfunctions. The camera view was shifted downward from April 7 to 11, 2018. The camera was non-functioning from February 7 to May 18, 2020.

Text S2. Water activity

The water activity of BSF brines was estimated with geochemical modeling and previously derived empirical relationships between brine density and water activity for BSF brines (Turk, 1973). Geochemistry of water samples from BSF (Kipnis et al., 2020) were equilibrated with halite using the React module in Geochemist's Workbench (Bethke, 2013) using the phrqpitz thermodynamic dataset. The water activity of halite-saturated brine was then calculated with the SpecE8 module. The mean calculated water

activity in Geochemist's Workbench was 0.75 with a standard deviation <0.01 . The density of natural and anthropogenic BSF surface brines was used as an input for an equation derived from Turk's (1973) measurements of BSF brines. The average water activity was 0.73 (standard deviation of 0.04). The maximum calculated water activity was 0.86. These results indicate that sustained surface brines at BSF have water activities between 0.73 to 0.75. A constant water activity of 0.74 was used in this research. Immediately after meteoric precipitation, BSF brine water activity is likely >0.74 . Changes in water activity are buffered by dissolution of surface halite.

Text S3. Groundwater data

Recent and historical measurements of groundwater levels, temperatures, water chemistry, anthropogenic brine fluxes, and well meta-data compiled from published data, the United States Geological Survey's national water information system (NWIS), and the Water Quality Portal are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4268710> (Bernau & Bowen, 2021; Kipnis & Bowen, 2018; Lines, 1978, 1979; Mason et al., 1995; Mason & Kipp, 1998; Read et al., 2017; Turk, 1973). The wells referred to in the main text as the 0.8 m and 3.5 m deep wells are identified as BLM-93C and BLM-93, respectively, in past publications. Supplemental figures incorporating current and historical groundwater data include Figures S2 and S6 to S10.

An electric groundwater level meter (dipper-T, Heron Instruments Inc., Ontario, Canada) was used to collect groundwater level measurements prior to deploying and immediately before recovering pressure transducers. There were some data gaps between 2017 to 2022 in continuous groundwater measurements from repositioning data loggers

or loggers reaching data storage capacity. The code used to analyze and correct groundwater level measurements is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5671739>.

S3.1. Barometric efficiency correction

Once the barometric efficiency was calculated it was applied to the dataset to determine what the water level would be without changes in barometric efficiency (Equations S3-1 and S3-2).

$$\Delta w_b = \text{cumsum}\left(\left(\frac{d}{dx}(b)\right) * (1 - BE)\right) \quad (S3-1)$$

where

Δw_b is the change in water level originating from air pressure over the study interval relative to its starting point;

$\frac{d}{dx}(b)$ is the change in air pressure (in units of an equivalent column of halite-saturated water) per unit time interval; and

BE is the barometric efficiency.

The cumulative sum of this is calculated to determine how water levels would change over time for changes in air pressure.

$$w_{BE} = w - \Delta w_b + \text{mean}(\Delta w_b)/2 \quad (S3-2)$$

where

w_{BE} is the water level with the barometric efficiency signal removed;

w is the original water level (as expressed in equivalent head of halite-saturated water); and

Δw_b is the change in water level originating from air pressure over the study interval relative to its starting point.

The effect air pressure on the water level at each moment is subtracted from the measured water level; because this would cause an offset in reported groundwater depth the mean value of the cumulative sum of water level change column is calculated and divided by two to determine the proper offset, which is added to the calculated water level at any moment. This methodology assumes that the barometric efficiency is invariable over time, which may not be the case for wells in unconfined aquifers.

Figure S1. Long-term climate measurements from Wendover, Utah, and comparisons of monthly average values of evaporation and potential evaporation, and monthly sums of precipitation at the western margin (margin) and center (crust) of the Bonneville Salt Flats from April to October 1993 and April to August 1994. (a) Crust evaporation (E) was higher than playa margin evaporation. (b) Potential evaporation (PE) was higher at the playa margin. (c) Cumulative precipitation (PPT) between the crust and the margin was within 5% of each other from October 1992 to July 1994. (d) Wendover, Utah, annual precipitation record demonstrates that the study period was drier than average but included unusually wet and dry years and that there has been a long-term decline in precipitation (PPT in 2021, not shown, was 44 mm). (e) Average annual temperatures from Wendover, Utah, reveal that the study period was warmer than average. (Figure data from Mason & Kipp, 1998; NOAA Climate Data Online Portal and MesoWest).

Figure S2. Anthropogenic brine volumes and solute mass balances over time in comparison to precipitation (PPT) and groundwater level measurements. (a) Net annual BSF anthropogenic brine volumes since 2001. (b) Mass of anthropogenic solutes added and removed from BSF (updated from Kipnis & Bowen, 2018). (c) Millimeters of water added to southwestern area of BSF annually, assuming added brine covers an area between 20 and 50 km² (as suggested by Bowen et al., 2017). If anthropogenically introduced brine were evenly distributed over a 120 km² BFLAT area, then it would contribute to 0-10% of annual recharge. (d) Density-corrected changes in groundwater level over time (key in (e)) (see Figure 6a for well locations). Wells BLM-41, BLM-34, and BLM-31 are located near brine extraction ditch (Figure 8a). (e) Modeled groundwater changes over time with temperature effects on water levels removed. (f) Monthly values of brine addition and removal during study period.

Figure S3. Weekly average values of measured and artificial neural network estimated (a) outgoing longwave (lw) radiation and of (b) net lw radiation.

Figure S4. Comparison between weekly total artificial neural network evaporation estimates made with different environmental inputs. E_e Low and E_e High shown for comparison. (a) Periods with measured evaporation. (b) Simple input scenario with no longwave radiation (LW) considered. (c) Comparison of input environmental measurements with longwave radiation considered. Using longwave radiation as an input improved artificial neural network evaporation outputs by making them more similar to the E_e Low model during known dry periods.

Figure S5. Measured and artificial neural network estimated evaporation over three time periods: (a) flooded conditions, (b) desiccated condition, (c) near-desiccation conditions.

Figure S6. Groundwater equivalent head correction. (a) Measured (filled circles) and calculated (lines) groundwater densities in 0.8 and 3.5 m deep wells. The density for the 0.8 and 3.5-m deep wells was calculated using the equations of state for these brines (Bernau & Bowen, 2021) with the soil temperature at 10 cm and measured water temperature at 100 cm depth used as the temperature inputs. (b) Comparison of measured water depth and halite-saturated water equivalent head from 0.8 and 3.5-m wells. (c) The difference between head calculated with constant density and head calculated with variable brine density is between 0.4 and 1.2 cm. (d) Centimeters of difference in head between the 3.5 and 0.8-m deep wells show vertical gradients vary seasonally.

Figure S7. 3.5 m well equivalent halite-saturated brine head corrected for barometric efficiency. (a) Relationship between daily change in air pressure and daily variation in groundwater depth. (b) Barometric correction removes significant variability from the water level, making it more representative of the water table in the halite crust. (c) Comparison of corrected values and measured groundwater level in 0.8 m well demonstrates agreement between barometric-corrected head and observed nearer-surface groundwater depth values.

Figure S8. Average monthly groundwater depths (corrected to equivalent head of halite-saturated brine) from wells along the SSW-NNE centerline of the Bonneville Salt Flats (Figure 6a), where the water table is consistently high (Lines, 1979; Mason & Kipp, 1998; Turk, 1973; and USGS water data portal). These measurements illustrate that year-to-year water levels vary least in August. Other months of the year are more variable. The lower summer of 1967 water levels in BR1 and BR2 (Turk, 1973), are from when the Salduro Loop water collection ditch was active. Groundwater collection rates from this time are unknown.

Figure S9. Relationship between 0.8 m well weekly average groundwater depth and weekly average (a) evaporation rate and (b) evaporation relative to potential evaporation. (b) Demonstrates a clear decline in evaporation when weekly average groundwater levels are below 5 cm depth.

Figure S10. Rapid rise in groundwater level at BLM-16 (~3 km southwest of 0.8 m well; Figure 6a) after 1.8 mm of PPT at BFLAT on July 16, 2021. BLM-16 may have received more PPT than BFLAT. (a) Measured and barometric-pressure corrected water level at BLM-16 and PPT over time. Several days shown before and after PPT to demonstrate background cyclicality in groundwater levels. (b to e) noted on (a) with their respective times: July 16 at (b) 7:46, (c) 15:26, (d) 15:46, and July 17 at (e) 7:06. Air pressure was also examined and could not be contributed to observed changes. Images shifted such that the same field of view show in each. Similar events with surface puddles forming after little rainfall, suspect Lisse effect, are noted in BFLAT timelapse imagery from October 5, 2021 (0.3 mm PPT). Time-lapse imagery are available in the repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4171331> under the names of *BLM16A_pond_20210716-20210717_alligned_rapideWaterLevelRise* and *BFLAT_20211005-20211009_RapidRiseInWaterLevel*.